

An Analytical study on Coping Mechanism among Employed and Unemployed Married Women in India

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Abstract

Marriage is a significant social institution that permits both men and women to have families. Marital satisfaction is a subjective sensation of joy and happiness experienced by the spouse, while considering every contemporary facet of marriage. There has been a massive development in education and employment, after the post-independence in India. The present study examines the coping mechanism among employed and unemployed married women. The objectives of the study are to understand the coping mechanism in employed and unemployed married women, and to study the different dimensions of coping mechanisms in employed and unemployed married women. The 60 married women were randomly selected for the test. According to the study's findings, married women who are employed encounter greater challenges than those who are not employed. It is concluded that employed married women cannot significantly contribute to their family's well-being in various respects. Working in two circumstances caused them to become distracted. They are unable to offer their married life the required attention.

Keywords: Coping Mechanism, Employed and Unemployed Married Women

Introduction

Marriage is a significant social institution that enables both men and women to have families. And the most durable condition between females and males more so than just acting, and propagation. They begin their basic family life by getting married. The benefits of marriage include the control of sex life and sex relationships, the creation of families, the creating of economic corporations, the contribution to partner stimulation on an emotional and intellectual level, and the pursuit of social solidarity. Demographic individual factors like material and the security interactions like such as the husband's assignment of household work, etc. are among the factors that affect material contentment. Marriage satisfaction refers to the subjective joy and pleasure felt by a couple while taking into account all aspects of their existing marriage.

Tradition, customs, and rituals are extremely important in Indian marriages. Marriages in India involve more than just the wedding couple; involve the joining of their families. Indian families have traditionally followed arranged marriages. After all, how people choose to be married has changed significantly throughout time.

The marital arrangements practiced worldwide include monogamy, polygamy, and polyandry, etc... The type of marriage that is permitted in culture depends traditionally on its geographic location, religious makeup, presence of men and women, and economic standing.

Meaning of marriage

Marriage is a social institution that can mean different things in different cultures. Although its objectives, functions, and forms may differ from each society, it is a universal institution. The more or less lasting relationship between a man and a woman that continues past the simple act of reproduction till after the delivery of children is known as marriage. (Sakhshree, 2017)

Marital maladjustment

Marital maladjustment is an imbalance and conflict between the couple that causes issues in their marriage. When two people from different backgrounds begin living together and encounter difficulties in their marriage, may lead to maladjustment. Teenagers and those in the 20–30 age range are more likely to experience it. Marriages that are well-adjusted and made to last a lifetime. Marital maladjustment is the inability of the spouse (husband and wife) to adjust to each other, which causes marital strife. (Samuel Aryee, 1992)

Factors affecting marital maladjustment

The major factors affecting marital maladjustment included the Unwillingness to cope with one another, minor pet peeves, mental instability, physical or health problems, criminal behaviour, a low level of commitment, immorality, different personal and professional goals, drug, sexual, physical, and emotional abuse, at times home tasks, childrearing, immaturity, and intellectual and sexual incompetence are some examples. Numerous research revealed that there are a variety of reasons why couples in corporations are experiencing marital adjustment. Heavy workloads, stressful environments, competitiveness, cutting-edge technology, long hours, night shifts, dual careers for both spouses, cybersex, financial security, changes in marital roles, and a lack of family time are some of the factors that contribute to marriage maladjustment. Studies have revealed that even while computer professionals earn sizable pay, they experience greater job stress and lower levels of job satisfaction.

Social support and work-family balance

The availability of supportive relationships and improvements to the calibre of such ties constitute social support (Leavy, 1983; p. 5). Organizational support and family-related assistance are two ways that social support might be divided (Brough and Pears, 2004). Personal social support comes from a spouse, children, parents, extended family, and friends, and employment-related social support comes from the company members, including colleagues and supervisors, where an employer works. However, researchers discovered that the husband's support was positively related to reducing quarrel in the wife's duties (Aryee, 1992; Barling, 1986).

Work-family balance and Employee performance

Employee productivity is measured by an employee's performance. in comparison to their peers in a variety of professions with similar behaviours (Babin and Boles, 1998, p. 82). It is crucial to consider how well employees perform at work and how well they can juggle work and family responsibilities. Employees who do well at work often feel content with their jobs, which makes it easier to balance work and family obligations. The study revealed very little support for the present link in the literature. Employee surveys were done by Baptiste (2008), reviewed the relationship between Human Resource Management practices, performance and employee well-being at the work-place. According to the writer, management relationship behaviour that fosters trust and support among employees promotes worker wellness at work.

Job satisfaction and work-family balance

An overall sentiment regarding one's profession in the case of particular aspects of her career is known as job satisfaction (Thompson et al., 2003). Nadeem and Abbas (2009) discovered that job satisfaction was highly or adversely connected with family and work to family and work interference, respectively, while Saltzstein et al. (2001) found that a heterogeneity of policies commonly have to be "family-friendly" were utilised. Researchers have also looked at the relationship between job satisfaction and work-family balance (Thomas et al., 1995; Saltzstein et al., 2001; Clark, 2001; Karimi, 2009). The use of family-friendly policies had significant effects on employee job satisfaction and employee satisfaction with work-family balance.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Aim of the Study

To study the coping mechanism among employed and unemployed married women.

Objectives of the study

- To understand the coping mechanism among employed and unemployed married women.
- To know the different aspects of coping mechanisms among employed and unemployed married women.

Hypothesis

Ho. There is no significant difference between employed and unemployed married women in coping mechanisms.

H1. There is a significant difference in aspects of coping mechanisms among employed and unemployed married women.

Samples

The sample of 60 married women (30 employed and 30 unemployed married women) was taken for the study from Child foundation, Hyderabad for employed. And unemployed married women were taken from Hyderabad. The sampling method was convenient random sampling.

Findings

This study looked into the coping mechanisms used by married women who were in jobs and those who weren't. According to the findings, there is no distinction between married women who are employed and unemployed in their marital lives. The findings refute the hypotheses that married women who are employed experience more difficulties than married women who are not employed. It implies that both people's levels of issues are comparable. It is reasonable to speculate that if a working married woman experiences issues in her marriage due to her excessive workload at the office, it is likewise correct to expect that unemployed married women may experience issues due to any family member's inappropriate behaviour or conflict at home.

This study looked into the coping mechanisms used by married women. According to the findings, there is no distinction between married women who are employed and unemployed in their marital lives. The findings refute the hypotheses that married women who are employed experience more difficulties than married women who are not employed. It implies that both people's levels of issues are comparable. It is reasonable to speculate that if a working married woman experiences issues in her marriage due to her excessive workload at the office, it is likewise correct to expect that unemployed married women may experience issues due to any family member's inappropriate behaviour or conflict at home. The immense time and emotional demands of their employment became intolerable due to decreased autonomy, an ever-increasing workload, and the additional burden of looking for a little child at home.. They struggle to function effectively at home because of this.

According to the hypothesis, there are no significant differences in the various marital coping scale characteristics for unemployed women. The results show that married women without a job experience more difficulties in their everyday lives and at home. Because a married woman who has a higher level of education may easily assess and resolve her domestic issues. In this way, she manages her marriage well and leads a contented marital life. However, married women are unable to resolve their issues due to a lack of knowledge about them. Her marital life is impacted by how she feels about herself. Additionally, the findings imply that married women who are unemployed are better adapted to their marital lives. It suggests that those unemployed women can enjoy their marital lives and deal with issues without difficulty. Researchers claim that marital coping mechanisms assist unemployed women address their problems and raise their children effectively.

The findings of the study show that employed women experience more difficulties than unemployed married women. There may be numerous causes. First off, people who work can find employment that are more meaningful credit to their education. Second, their education aids them in resolving domestic issues. However, other results show both of them having issues with marital adjustment in their marriage. The marital life of employed women is difficult to spend, and their marital coping is poor. The fact that they are having trouble in two distinct but crucial situations is the cause in this instance. They are unable to properly attend to their marriage and home as a result. Their marriage is ill-adjusted as a result.

Conclusion

Thus, it can be said that there are distinctions between married people who are employed and unemployed. According to the study's findings, married women who are employed encounter greater challenges in life than married women who are not employed. It is concluded that employed married women cannot make a major contribution to their family's well-being in various respects. Working in two circumstances caused them to become distracted. They are unable to offer their marriages the required attention.

References

- Ayree S (1992). Antecedents and Outcomes of Work-Family Conflict among Married Professional Women: Evidence from Singapore. *Hum. Relations*, 45: 813-837.
- Bernard J. *Work and family: Changing roles of men and women*. Palo Alto, CA: Mayfield.1984.
- Blood RO, Wolfe DM. *Husbands and Wives*. New York. 1960.
- Barrera M, Garrison Jones CV. Properties of the Beck Depression Inventory as a Screening Instrument for Adolescent Depression. *Journal of Abnormal Child Psychology* 1988;16:263-73.
- Burke RJ, Weir T. Relationship of wives employment status to husband, wife and pair satisfaction and performance. *Journal of Marriage and Family* 1987;38(5):278-87.
- Babin J, Boles JS (1998). Employee Behavior in a Service Environment: A Model and Test of Potential Differences between Men and Women. *J. Mark.*, 62: 77-91.
- Banyard VL, Graham-Bermann SA (1993). Can Women Cope? A Gender Analysis of Theories of Coping with Stress . *Psychol. Women Quart.*, 17: 303-318.
- Baptiste NR (2008). Tightening the Link between Employee Wellbeing at Work and Performance: A new Dimension for HRM. *Manage. Decis.*, 46(2): 284-309.
- Berg P, Kalleberg AL, Appelbaum E (2003). Balancing Work and Family: The Role of High-Commitment Environments. *Ind. Relations*, 42(2), 168-188.
- Brough P, Pears J (2004). Evaluating the Influence of the Type of Social Support on Job Satisfaction and Work Related Psychological Wellbeing. *Int. J. Organ. Behav.*, 8(2): 472-485.
- Campbell A, Converse PE, Rogers WL. *The Quality of American Life*. New York: Russel Sage Foundation. 1976.
- Comer RJ. *Abnormal psychology* 2nd edition. WH Freeman and company. USA.1996.
- Cooper CL. *The Stress Check*. Englewood Cliffs: Prentice-Hall. 1981.
- Dalack GW. Perspectives on the Relationship between Cardiovascular Disease and Affective Disorder. *The Journal of Clinical Psychiatry* 1990;51:4-9.
- Global Journal of Management and Business Research Volume 11 Issue 6 Version 1.0 May 2011 Type: Double Blind Peer Reviewed International Research Journal Publisher: Global Journals Inc. (USA) Print ISSN: 0975-5853 Stress And Depression Experienced By Women Software Professionals In Bangalore, Karnataka
- Gore S, Manigione TW. Social roles, sex roles, and psychological distress: Additive and interactive models of sex differences. *Journal of Health and Social Behavior* 1983;24:300-12.